

FREUD'S ORIGINALITY IN CONSIDERATION OF PLEASURE AS THE FOUNDATION OF PASSIONAL LIFE

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12523076

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ABSTRACT

This article addresses the theme involving Freud's originality in considering pleasure as the foundation of passionate life. Its scientific relevance lies in the fact that it academically discusses Freud's thoughts and theories about sexuality as a conditioning element of human existence. Its social relevance lies in the fact that it brings psychoanalytic concepts, stripped of their purely sexual content, into the field of the broad public, now under a more philosophical, more human bias. This is a bibliographical, factual, analytical and descriptive research. Freud takes as a principle for his analyzes and subsequent clinical deductions the fact that every human being seeks pleasure in his life, at all times; This cannot be understood as an end in itself, because in the author's view, what is at stake is maintaining the balance of personal life. Freud always sought to understand how individual and collective desires dialogue and conflict, as well as how they enable human beings to achieve their condition of well-being. Freud was the pioneer in studying, in a systematic way, how these situations intertwine in human beings, leading them to a single end which would be their search for a merit of satisfying their desires, without this depriving them of their freedom, because he needs to continue living under the illusion that he has absolute control over his wills, understanding that this condition of illusion is what allows him a certain pleasure in acting and being in tune with his ego.

Keywords: Freud; Psychoanalysis; Pleasure; Passionate life.

INTRODUCTION

Sigmund Freud (1856-1939) is the product of a troubled time in Europe, in which the imminent rise of a new type of urban individual stands out; one who has to share social space with others who migrated from the fields to the city in search of jobs and the golden dream. Many things were considered true, but none of them considered emotional life as a relevant element in the formation of personality and character. This is where this elementary point lies in the Freudian analysis of everyday life, in which *pleasure*, or the systematic search for it, often at a high cost to the individual's psychic economy, becomes the target of Freud's

investigation, as way of approaching an explanation for the psychopathology that has become inherent in everyday life.

All Freudian thought, as well as his technique, were born from inconsistencies generated by this same moment of high complexity in human existence in 19th century Europe and that, however strange it may seem, society demanded an explanation for the phenomena that affected it and that sciences such as Sociology, Philosophy, Psychology and Theology were unable to explain satisfactorily. The desire of the bourgeoisie to freely experience all the freedom that their money and prestige allowed clashed with the condition of guilt, generating symptoms that could not be explained by the Medicine of the time. Therefore, Freud takes as a principle for his analyzes and subsequent clinical deductions the fact that every human being seeks pleasure in his life, at all times; however, this cannot be understood as an end in itself, because in the Master's conception, what is at stake is the maintenance of the balance of autonomous existence, which can end up disrupting the individual relationship with the social environment. Thus, he needs to develop a theory that could explain everything he observed, based on his clinical practice, where he addresses the *principle of pleasure*, in which he defends the primacy of pleasure for the individual, in which he seeks immediate satisfaction for himself, regardless of the consequences and only with difficulty would there be a restriction on the satisfaction of this latent desire, which would generate a conflict, a source of displeasure and the solution to this would be the condition of pleasure, not what the patient wanted, *a priori*, however, it makes it possible to maintain psychic balance in its most dynamic form possible. In this sense, it can be considered that the individual's entire emotional life is governed by this principle, that of the search for pleasure and the attempt to eliminate displeasure, understanding here, by this expression, as the removal of situations that cause discomfort and that produce conflicts. that are beyond their solution conditions.

Freud was the pioneer in studying, in a systematic way, how these situations intertwine in human beings, leading them to a single end which would be their search for a merit of satisfying their desires, without this depriving them of their freedom, because he needs to continue living under the illusion that he has absolute control over his wills, understanding that this condition of illusion is what allows him a certain pleasure in acting and being in tune with his ego. It is not enough to move away from a source that causes you discomfort to understand that you have achieved pleasure, it is necessary to be in action and in contact with elements that provide you with satisfaction and happiness, so that it is understood as an element of value. His entire quest to be recognized in the game between antagonistic forces that confront each other, delimiting who dominates which space and in which time.

Before him, other thinkers had already considered such things and even expressed them; however, these visions were launched without a deep explanation about how they occurred and *why*, and the entire religious bias that dominated the European scene ended up biasing the explanations, leading to interpretations that ended in the fight of good against the evil that was ravaging and haunted the human being. This was very little for a human being who, if he still believed in the existence of God, no longer feared him as his ancestors did and, with the advancement of natural sciences, man increasingly saw himself as a being of nature, subjected to laws that could be explained and to that end, he wanted not only to have knowledge about them, but also to have control over them.

Freud, better than any other thinker of his time, managed to carry out this reading of the intrinsic feeling of European man, defined by the desire to gain freedom from feelings considered *taboo* at the time and, even if he was distressed at having been placed on the margins of the great masters of his time, everything indicates that those same people who marginalized him were waiting to see what he could demonstrate with the innovative technique he presented. What he describes as human expression was not his greatest achievement; This would happen based on the explanation based on facts of the phenomena that until then were treated by religion as demonic possessions and by medicine as madness. Freud takes man from the hands of the priest and the doctor and frees him from his most bizarre superstitions, clarifying that everything he does, good and bad, is the result of a conflict generated due to his always constant search for pleasure.

CONSIDERATION OF PLEASURE AS THE FOUNDATION OF PASSIONAL LIFE

Our entire life is governed by passions of all forms, some more violent, others less; however, in one way or another, they are the ones that govern the existence of human beings, who live in search of ways to satisfy them, not because it is an imperative of nature, but because they awaken sensations of pleasure and do not provoke it, as one would think in a common analysis situation. In the conception of Santos (2010), “passions are the trigger of a human mechanism that involves desire, pleasure, imagination and sensation. All of these provide [*in*]voluntary movements that direct man, as a being, to undertake his interaction with the environment and others” (p. 01).

This interaction never happens smoothly, nor linearly for anyone, because man's relationship with his feelings is marked by ambiguities and challenges, starting with the fact that he does not exercise the control he believes over his wills and what he most believes to be

feelings of superiority do not pass from feelings of inferiority that turn him into a frightened victim of his own unconscious world. Sometimes it is, when you gain control over these obscure feelings that are brought to your consciousness, clarifying their nuances and points of conflict that you begin to enjoy a certain pleasure, not because you have exposed your weakness and indolence, but because you discover where The matrix of your conflict state is found and, therefore, you can take care of solving your weakness, thus becoming more powerful. This, in fact, is the main function of psychoanalytic technique: to help the individual overcome their most cruel obstacles, which are a source of displeasure, making them autonomous, which will thus bring them to the field of pleasure as a liberating force.

Freud works with the expression *pleasure*, as a *leitmotif*, which enables an understanding of the finest processes of human experience that begin at birth and accompany it until death. For him, every human action seeks a type of satisfaction that produces, as a result, pleasure and, if this does not occur, the action is denied in its entirety, simply because it generates frustration. For Freud, all existence is marked by the search for pleasure; Blaise Pascal (1623-1662) already stated that every man seeks happiness, even those who are about to commit suicide; possibly find some pleasure in your death, which the end of a distressing sensation may mean. Although the statements use apparently different terms, both are dealing with the same object and the same target.

For Freud, however, all pleasure was linked, in some way, to the sphere of sexuality, a search for satisfaction and in this he did not fail to consider that this drive begins with birth in which the first feeling of satisfaction that the human being finds It's with the act of sucking. The newborn, as soon as it is placed in contact with the mother's or nursing mother's breast, ceases to cry, which was understood as the state of discomfort having been interrupted, however, he goes further and argues that there, In that act, there was something deeper, more instinctive, more primitive, a sensation that was far from being able to be interpreted by a simplistic analytical reason. Therefore, he concludes that crying is interrupted because it is replaced by a pleasurable sensation and that the fact of suppressing hunger is a secondary effect, not a primary one, because otherwise, the child would only stop crying after satisfying his hunger and this would not be the case. It occurs because she stops it as soon as she has access to the breast. Following the path of this Freudian theory, Magnino (1999, p. 46) highlights that “Freud raises the hypothesis that the compulsion to repeat indicates that it seems that there is something more primitive, more elementary, more instinctual, in each being, than the pleasure principle.”

From this thought, it is possible to understand that people have a tendency to cling to what is pleasant, to what generates pleasure, comfort, as children cling to their parents, and it is not because they provide them with pleasure. , in a direct way, rather, because actions aimed at care, hygiene, nutrition, protection lead to another deeper and more primitive element that persists in human thought as a way of feeling happy and its lack leads to a state of displeasure, generating discomfort; This element is security.

Another aspect raised is that the search for feelings of pleasure are caused by drives, that is, they are not constant, and even for the animal, which seeks to satisfy its instincts through food, rest and occasional sex, Humans remain in this same line with the difference that they have developed speech and thus can express what they actually feel, and which are its most direct dimensions towards the primacy of pleasure.

At this point, one must try to clarify what Freud understood as pleasure, so that guidelines are not created that do not or cannot clearly express Freudian thought. For him, pleasure was far beyond the denial of dissatisfaction or the removal of it, or even the consummation of the desired act. It was a compulsive search for human beings, normal and abnormal, differentiating both groups by the fact that the first suffered from the same things as the second, with the way in which each one dealt directly with situations as a point of convergence, the which leads him to the search for an answer not to the suffering of neurotics, but to an understanding of the situation of normal people and thus elaborates the concept of sublimation, which consists of the ability to transform something unpleasant into something pleasant. Such an attitude would lead the individual to an artificial form of satisfaction; however, he would be responsible for maintaining his psychic economy.

Possibly, this is an evolution towards supporting civilized life, with all its strict and standardized rules, considering that the desires that lead to pleasure are, at all times, targets of restriction by authority figures, starting with the family and then being continued by the school, in an infinite process that only ends with death. It is in this sense that Freud reveals that

The first example of the pleasure principle being inhibited is familiar and occurs regularly. We know that the pleasure principle is a primary method of functioning on the part of the mental apparatus, but that, from the point of view of the organism's self-preservation amidst the difficulties of the external world, it is, from the beginning, ineffective and even highly dangerous (FREUD [1920], 2006, p. 07).

Thus, for Freud, he had found a way to justify his theory of sublimation, which for individuals would help them preserve their social and private life conditions, remembering that all repression causes anguish and suffering, not because it deprives the individual directly from

a primary source of pleasure, but, beyond that, because it forces you to go in search of new sources of satisfaction of your most intrinsic needs. This would work as a fact for normal individuals; in the case of neurotics, “the repetition, the re-experience of something identical, is clearly, in itself, a source of pleasure” (*Idem* , p. 24), even if it is something that has caused pain and situations distressing.

Freud's originality in considering pleasure as a fundamental primacy of human life arises from his analysis of the mind and behavior of neurotics. It is a bit strange and complex to analyze Freud's work and thought and what leads many scientists to not understand him is the withholding of this information, that he interpreted social reality based on his neurotic patients and in this way deduced and built an ideal model on which a balanced life or what could balance the forces between the idealized and the realized, were exposed in the condition of obedience to social rules and principles, which leads everyone to not feel happy with the conditions of life to which they are constantly subjected.

It is on this constant conflict between what is possible and what is restricted by the force of the law that the situation of neurosis and anguish exists, with human beings having to seek satisfaction of pleasures within limits that go beyond the anxiety of each person. . Freud believed, and his entire theory goes in this direction, that all pleasure is a form of satisfaction of the repressed sexual instinct, sublimated under aspects directed towards ends that appear to be far from the individual preservation of the species, but which hide deeper desires that are difficult to expose. , because if exposed they could create situations of discomfort and misunderstanding, ostracism, isolation, abandonment. In this situation, the individual weighs between a situation of full satisfaction and its direct consequences and a restriction on them, using a game of words and emotions and enjoying a greater good which would be the maintenance of their bond with the social fabric.

In this aspect, Freud (1920) reveals that “the pleasure principle persists for a long time as the method of functioning employed by the sexual instincts, which are difficult to 'educate'” (FREUD [1920], 2006, p. 07) (Emphasis no. original), allowing us to understand, from his words, that the repression of drives would, in some way, bring issues of satisfaction, not taking the concepts as a sign of masochism, however, in the aspect that depriving oneself of a certain pleasure, immediate , this would provide you with longer, longer-lasting pleasure.

When the mind is dominated by the pleasure principle, which can be understood here as the search for the satisfaction of desires, humans are led to act strictly impulsively, without measuring the immediate consequences of their attitudes. It is known that impulsive actions disregard rules and do not obey any logic, this is because the unconscious does not know either

of them. Thus, the principle of reality emerges, which has the mission of rationalizing the archaic impulses of the pleasure principle in order to delimit, based on cultural rules, which of these impulses can be satisfied, when they can and where they are acceptable. Freud concludes, therefore, that all human thought is, on the one hand, conflict and, on the other, commitment, highlighting that conflict arises because he wants to satisfy everything that could give him pleasure and on the other hand, he has commitment, guided by ethics, in respecting canonical social rules. Education consists of making respect for such sanctions satisfactory, or one might understand, pleasurable; In the end, the search for pleasure prevails.

CONCLUSION

The sentimental life of human beings is full of all kinds of conflicts, leaving man with nothing left to fight to overcome them and, in doing so, reach a state of happiness that overcomes his anxieties, awakening sensations of pleasure, feelings which Freud had a principle of originality when seeking its foundations to explain human passions.

Unlike so many others who spoke about the existence of passions and ended their arguments there, more concerned with describing them, the Master of Vienna explains how they arise and remain in life, not just provoking the most diverse feelings in the human spirit, but, expanding or reducing their network of contacts, because of the sensations of pleasure that may or may not confer on them, directly and indirectly.

It is observed that Freud places pleasure as the basis for passions and not the other way around, that is, it is understood that it is always in search of satisfaction of unconscious pleasures that one seeks that justifies and influences the emergence of new passions. In this way, in a strange and complex way, the human being finds himself a slave to his desires which, once satisfied, lead him to a state of ecstasy and this needs to be experienced again and again as an addiction, for which there is no known remedy and which cannot be avoided.

Freud called this entire scope the pleasure principle which, if not satisfied, causes states of anguish, but over time, as man also lives under the principle of reality, he learned to disguise his desires and transmute them into situations that keeps him on the margins of full satisfaction, however, allow him to continue to delude himself between what he has a hope of possessing that which is beyond him, never attainable, not because there are insurmountable obstacles, simply because he no longer has a pleasure that can be put in its place as an object of search, since it was castrated in its most primitive will by the cultural process to which the entire modern society was subjected, in the civilizing process.

Freud never tired of saying that the formation of the human personality resembled a process of geological formation, in which layers were superimposed on already existing structures and these, in turn, remained intact and active, in their primordial functions, as long as the slightest shock allows the most primitive feelings to surface and brings human beings to their knees. In this sense, what Psychoanalysis seeks to do is guide individuals on the best way to deal with instinctual-drive life, providing a fair balance of the libidinal psychic economy.

Throughout his work, Freud always sought to understand how individual and collective desires dialogue and conflict, as well as how they enable human beings to achieve their condition of well-being, even when pressured in this winding race of coping with having to achieve their condition. of satisfaction in the midst of the demands of which he becomes a victim, because he is not up to them and because they, in the same way, prevent complete enjoyment. This gives rise to another type of conflict more marked by the violence with which it is imposed on the individual, which is his obedience and accommodation to the pleasure that can be achieved, within powerful limits placed by the culture in which he finds himself involved.

Freud believed that all psychic action aims to escape pain and avoid any action that causes displeasure. But we cannot ignore the fact that human beings are sadists and pain addicts, vengeful, full of the most harmful feelings known and, at times, they allow themselves to engage in actions that cause them pain, because This action of yours, which seems excessive, may cause more pain in someone you dislike, a sadistic type of revenge, however this allows you and still makes it possible to reach your state of pleasure, which does not allow us to depart from the Master's originality. of Vienna, that his considerations about pleasure as the foundation of individual passionate life were correct.

REFERENCES

FREUD, Sigmund. [1920]. *In addition to the pleasure principle, group psychology and other works*. In : Brazilian Standard Edition of the Complete Psychological Works of Sigmund Freud. Rio de Janeiro: Imago, 2006.

MAGNINO, Lídia Queiroz Silva. Pleasure principle: theoretical and clinical reflections. In: *Pulsional Revista de Psic Análise* , year XIII, 1999, n°. 132, 45-51.

SANTOS, Renato dos. *PLEASURE as the foundation of passionate life* . Available at : <https://www.webartigos.com> . Accessed on 08/08/2018.